

POLITICAL EDUCATION AND ITS ROLES IN NATION BUILDING: THE PERCEPTION OF TEACHERS IN IBADAN NORTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT

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Abstract

Education helps an individual in any society to become better in preserving the values, ideals and beliefs that are regarded as fundamental to the continuous existence of such society. It also helps an individual to become a useful agent of reconstructing or transforming the existing skills, competencies and ideologies which will serve as a launch pad to facilitate the development of the society and the individual while political education is a specialized form of education targeted towards bringing about a better polity into existence. The survey research design was employed in the study. The population of the study was the social science subject related teacher in Ibadan North Local Government, Ibadan Oyo State. The single stage cluster sampling and random sampling techniques were used to select 10 schools and 50 respondents that made up the sample size. The questionnaire titled 'Political Education Need Assessment Questionnaire' (PENAQ) was the major research instrument used. Data generated was analysed using descriptive statistics of mean, standard deviation and frequency count. The study revealed that political education is vital to building informed and political active citizens and in building and sustaining a virile democratic nation. The study recommended that the government should do more in providing political education for her citizens especially under a formal school system.

Keywords: Political education, Nation building perception.

Introduction

Education at all level is geared towards making and helping an individual become a useful and productive member of the society. This is why Kolawole (2014) sees education as a process of becoming. Education helps an individual in any society to become better in preserving the values, ideals and beliefs that are regarded as fundamental to the continuous existence of such society. It also helps an individual to become a useful agent of reconstructing or transforming the existing skills, competencies and ideologies which will serve as a launch pad to facilitate the development of the society and the individual. In other words, education is a refining tool; it helps an individual to become sociable, governable, informed and skillful, on the other hand, education remains a tool that helps a nation to accelerate its development, build a crop of informed and skillful citizenry and build a strong veritable nation. Every democratic government or society willing to develop itself and climb the ladder

of development, progress and stable political system have the responsibility of educating its citizens and succeeding generations. As noted by Schoeman (2006), a free and strong democratic society has to rely on the knowledge, the skills and virtues of its citizens and those they elect to serve in public offices on their behalf. The government of Nigeria has realised this and that is why it was clearly outlined in the National Policy on Education that 'it has adopted education, par excellence, as an instrument for promoting national development' (NPE, 2004). If education is a vital tool in building and advancing the economic and technological development of a nation, then, political education is a tool needed to build and sustain a strong democratic society.

All men are by nature political and politics in itself is ubiquitous. No man can claim aloofness from politics for politics is involved wherever you have two or more people, for wherever you have two or more people there will be conflicts of interests and each seeking to protect his/her interests in the midst of varying interest is in the realm of politics. Politics is ubiquitous because it is found everywhere, i.e. in the family, organized groups, in the state and among various states in the world, hence the word local, organizational, national and international politics. Therefore, anyone living in the modern states cannot be absolved from politics because directly or indirectly politics shapes his/her lives. Political education on its own is capable of different meaning, to some, political education refers to the process of political socialisation, others term the idea to mean citizenship education or democratic citizenship while others refers to it as civic education. Even though it may not be contradictory to refer to it in the above named ways, yet the idea of political education cannot be limited to any of those. The concept of political education is apt and more encompassing. In their words, Ozmon and Craver (1976), see it as a specialized form of education targeted towards bringing about a better polity into existence. In his own view, Nwankwo (2012) believes Political education should concern itself explicitly with explaining core political matters to the citizens using the school as an apparatus to bring about a sane political system. Political education is an intentional education aimed at motivating and mobilising people in democratic societies to engage in political activities, to critique and analyse social and political issues independently and to develop skills and values necessary for community and nation building. Wenli Yu (1997) has highlighted the concern of political education to include the inculcation of knowledge, attitude and skill in such matters as political representation and participation. Therefore, topics or matters relating to state, government authority, legitimacy, power, rights, civil liberty and law fall into the category of political education. Many political theorists have written to support the critical role of political education in developing the cognitive and affective (moral) qualities of citizens. Citizens cannot just be responsible until they are trained, tutored and informed to respect, nurture and support the ideals of democracy through exposure to political education.

To have a detailed understanding of the concept nation-building, there is the need to have the knowledge of what a nation is. A nation in its basic sense means the group of people or race who share the same history, customs, traditions, language and religion. According to Stephenson (2005), the people of a nation generally share a common national identity, and part of nation-building is the building of that common identity. Omoniji (2005) puts it that a nation consists of people living in the same territory, having the same language, with the same consciousness and the same culture. Some have attempted to distinguish between an ethnic nation, based in (the social construction of) race or ethnicity, and a civic nation, (nation state) based in common identity and loyalty to a set of political ideas and institutions, and the linkage of citizenship to nationality. Also, Anifowose (1999) observed

that a nation is concerned with those factors as common history, common territory, common language or literature, common culture and similar characteristics. From these definitions and explanation, it could clearly be seen that Nigeria is not a nation but a multi-nation state because of the different ethnic groups that can be found in Nigeria which Bamgbose (2000) reported to be over 250. However, a nation is defined, one thing that is sacrosanct is the fact that a nation is a group of people who have certain things in common and are willing to stay together in building such things that defines them. This is the basis for nation building.

Nation-building is a normative concept which means different things to different people depending on who is saying what. Some basically sees nation-building programmes as those in which dysfunctional or failed states are given assistance in the development of government infrastructure, dispute resolution mechanism and economic assistance, in order to increase stability. Stephenson (2005) submitted that this idea belongs to the post-war context in Iraq, Afghanistan etc. In a post-colonial context like the case with many African countries and Nigeria inclusive Nation-building involves the psychological reconstruction of individuals, a process of infusing into the people of new independent territories who differ widely in language, customs and traditions with a new sense of sharing the same identity. Nation-building referred to the efforts of newly-independent nations, notably the nations of Africa but also in the Balkans, (Harris, 2012) to reshape territories that had been carved out by colonial powers or Empires without regard to ethnic, religious, or other boundaries (Deutsch & Foltz, 2010). According to Omoniji (2005) and Otelaja (2008), nation-building involves the building of the individual and the structuring of his environment, the creation or recreation of a political community, of a cohesive and enduring ethos capable of making the individual identify with the political community. Nation-building involves the deliberate building of spirit of patriotism, solidarity and understanding among the large ethnic that make up a country, where everyone becomes loyal to the country and stop subordination of national interest to regional interest. Importantly, it is notable that nation-building generally assumes that someone or something is doing the building intentionally.

Nigeria since independence has made several attempts at rebuilding what was bequeathed to them by the British colonial masters. According to Eme and Onyishi (2014), nation-building includes the creation of national symbols such as flags, anthems, national days, national stadiums, national airlines, national languages, and national myths. Also, Bandyopadhyay and Green (2011) while evaluating nation-building policies of African states itemized some of the policies many African states have initiated to facilitate nation-building. It includes:

1. Changing state names.
2. Changing Capital Cities Names and Locations
3. Changing National Currencies
4. Conscription and National Service
5. Religious and Linguistic Homogenization
6. Republican and Centralization Policies
7. One-Party States
8. Non-Ethnic Censuses
9. Land Nationalization

A critical look at these nine points listed above clearly revealed that Nigeria in her nation-building quest have implemented at least seven of the so called "African nation-building policies" however, this has not culminated into political, economic and technological development when Nigeria is compared with the likes of nations such as Malaysia, India, etc. who were third world countries around the time Nigeria got independence in 1960. There is the need for Nigeria after 100 years of existence to begin to explore other means and directions to facilitate her nation-building quest.

The political experiences of Nigeria since her emergence as a state (political entity) in 1914 and as a sovereign state since 1960 have not left much to be desired, the Nigerian political terrain has had a sour taste of misrule, corruption, civil war engendered by ethnic rivalry, election mal-practices, insurgencies, unemployment, ethnic militias and lately terrorism. Every attempt by succeeding government in building a virile and unified nation state has met with ethnic suspicion, mistrust and doubts. Allegiance to local ethnic groups is greater than support and patriotism to the Nigerian state. The politicians take advantage of political ignorance among the electorate to cause division and further entrench the spirit of ethnic rivalry to their advantage. Therefore, this study investigated teachers' perception of the role of political education in nation-building in Nigeria based on developing selfless public leaders, increase support for democratic governance and solve Nigerian political challenges.

Research Questions

1. What is the role of political education in developing selfless public leaders needed for nation-building as perceived by teachers?
2. Can political education be used to increase support for democratic governance in order to build a crop of political active and responsive citizenry as perceived by teachers?
3. Can political education be used to solve Nigerian political challenges of terrorism, ethnic rivalry and tribalism as perceived by teachers?

Methodology

The descriptive survey research design was used in the study. The total sample was 50 Social Science subject based teachers, who were randomly selected from 10 secondary schools in Ibadan North Local Government Area of Ibadan, Oyo State. Data were collected using a self-designed instrument titled 'Political Education Need Assessment Questionnaire (PENAQ)' which was validated and the reliability was ascertained using Cronbach alpha and reliability coefficient of 0.81. Respondents were asked to rate all items using 4-point likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) rated 4, 3, 2, and 1. Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics of simple frequency count, mean and standard deviation.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the role of political education in developing selfless public leaders needed for nation-building as perceived by teachers?

Table 1: Teachers' Perception of the Role of Political Education in Developing Selfless and Public Spirited Leaders needed for Nation-building

S/N	STATEMENTS	SA F (%)	A F (%)	D F (%)	SD F (%)	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	Political education can help to develop leadership skills required for transparency, accountability and corruption-free practices in governance.	30 (60.0)	18 (36.0)	2 (4.0)	-	3.56	.58
2	Political education can help intending leaders to develop public spirit, and attitude of selfless service required for nation building.	24 (48.0)	19 (38.0)	7 (14.0)	-	3.34	.72
3	Political education can help Nigerians to develop necessary skills and initiatives needed for community development, and nation-building.	23 (46.0)	21 (42.0)	5 (10.0)	1 (2.0)	3.32	.74

The table showed that 48 or 96 % agreed that "Political education can help to develop leadership skills required for transparency, accountability and corruption-free practices in governance" while 2 or 4 % disagreed. Further, 43 or 86 % of the respondents agreed that "Political education can help intending leaders to develop public spirit, and attitude of selfless service required for nation-building" while 7 or 14 % disagreed. Still, 44 or 88 % of the respondents agreed that "Political education can help Nigerians to develop necessary skills and initiatives needed for community development, and nation-building" while 6 or 12 % disagreed.

Research question 2: Can political education be used to increase support for democratic governance in order to build a crop of political active and responsive citizenry as perceived by teachers?

Table 2: Teachers' Perception of the Role of Political Education in Increasing Support for Democratic Governance and Building a Crop of Political Active and Responsive Citizenry

S/N	STATEMENTS	SA F (%)	A F (%)	D F (%)	SD F (%)	Mean	Standard Deviation
4	Political education can help to increase support for democratic governance and solve the problem of political apathy among Nigerians	23 (46.0)	21 (42.0)	5 (10.0)	1 (2.0)	3.32	.74
5	Political education can be used as an instrument to eradicate political ignorance and evolve political active citizens	27 (54.0)	21 (42.0)	2 (4.0)	-	3.50	.58

The table above showed that 47 or 94 % of the respondents agreed that “Political education can help to increase support for democratic governance and solve the problem of political apathy among Nigerians” while 3 or 6 % disagreed. It also reveals that 48 or 96 % agreed that “Political education can be used as an instrument to eradicate political ignorance and evolve political active citizens” while 2 or 4 % disagreed.

Research question 3: Can political education be used to solve Nigerian political challenges of terrorism, ethnic rivalry and tribalism as perceived by teachers?

Table 3 Shows teachers' perception of the role of political education in solving the problems of ethnic rivalry and tribalism

S/N	STATEMENTS	SA F (%)	A F (%)	D F (%)	SD F (%)	Mean	Standard Deviation
6	Political education can solve the problems of terrorism and violence among Nigerian citizens.	24 (48.0)	25 (50.0)	1 (2.0)	-	3.46	.54
7	Political education can solve the problems of tribalism in Nigerian politics.	21 (42.0)	23 (46.0)	5 (10.0)	1 (2.0)	3.28	.73
8	Political education can solve the problems of religious bigotry and fanaticism associated with Nigerian politics.	15 (30.0)	27 (54.0)	8 (16.0)	-	3.14	.67

The above table showed that 49 or 98 % of the respondents agreed that "Political education can solve the problems of terrorism and violence among Nigerian citizens" while 1 or 2 % disagreed. Still more, 44 or 88 % of the respondents agreed that "Political education can solve the problems of tribalism in Nigerian politics" while 6 or 12 % disagreed. Lastly, the table reveals that 42 or 84 % of the respondents agreed that "Political education can solve the problems of religious bigotry and fanaticism associated with Nigerian politics while 8 or 16 % disagreed.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed that political education is strongly perceived as an instrument to evolve a new set of public spirited leaders who will be committed to the development and building of the new Nigeria. This finding are in agreement with Achebe (1979) who explained that the problem with Nigeria is squarely a failure of leadership and Nwankwo (2012), who says that however well contrived a political system may be, it is as good as nothing without the individual human beings (leaders) who are capable and willing to make it function. He also believes that the emergence of a just and good state is a function of the education that is made available to the citizens.

The data generated showed that political education is a potent tool to mobilise support for democracy and representative government who can actively participate in the political process of the nation. This finding corroborates the submission of Babalola (2014), that nations who over the time have built a strong democratic and viable and participatory political system did so by employing the tool of decisive and holistic political education to transform the attitude and disposition of their citizens. Giroux, (1995) and Schoeman (2006) while noting the importance of political education states that "schools must assist in the unending work of preparing citizens for self- governance in an evolving social environment.

Even though several steps have been taking by the government of Nigeria to integrate the ethnic groups in time past, the findings from the study reveals that political education have a critical role to play in integrating the various ethnic group in the country. This view is supported by Arko-Cobbah (2007) assumes that political education is not just an ordinary education but it involves a set of value and commitments. Political education focuses on the *knowledge, skills and dispositions* a citizen requires for living in a liberal democratic society.

Conclusion

The study has shown that Nation-building is a decisive and conscious effort by any government to reconstruct the society for growth, development and advancement in all ramifications. Nigeria has made several attempts at re-building what was inherited from the British colonial masters in 1960 but the efforts made so far cannot be said to have succeeded for many reasons. This is because many issues are threatening the continuous existence of this country. Corruption, terrorism, ethnicity, and bad governance are few of the challenges undermining the integrity of this supposed giant of Africa. Findings from the study have shown that political education remains a potent tool that Nigeria can use to evolve a new set of leaders in the political sector who are selfless and who can be committed to the nation building project of Nigeria. The study has also shown that through political education, the challenges of corruption, tribalism and political apathy can be resolved.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Political education should be integrated into the secondary school curriculum by the government as a matter of urgency to educate teeming Nigerian youths who are the future leaders of Nigeria.

2. Awareness campaign should also be carried out by relevant non-governmental agencies to educate youths who are out of the secondary school system of the need to acquire political education as the basis for informed and effective participation in the Nigerian system.
3. Curriculum agency like the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) should be properly mobilised by the government to provide a framework for integrating political education into the secondary school curriculum.

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